

Agile Methodologies in the Educational Context: A Systematic Literature Review

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Abstract

The application of agile methodologies in the educational context has emerged as an innovative strategy for developing technical, behavioral, and managerial competencies. This study aims to investigate the applicability of agile methodologies in the educational context. Through a systematic literature review in databases such as Scopus and Web of Science analyzed 27 peer-reviewed articles that met the predefined inclusion criteria were analyzed. The results show that agile methodologies promote organization, collaboration, creative problem-solving, and increased student engagement and autonomy. However, educators and institutions identified difficulties such as initial resistance to change, the need for training, and cultural challenges as barriers to effective implementation. Studies show that, when combined with methodologies such as Project-Based Learning (PBL), agile practices can significantly enhance students' motivation, communication, and collaboration skills. In addition, these approaches enable the creation of dynamic and flexible learning environments aligned with the needs of a constantly changing world. Finally, agile methodologies have great potential to transform teaching, offering adaptable structures that meet the demands of learning environments. This study reinforces the relevance of exploring and adapting agile methodologies to the specificities of the educational environment, contributing to the construction of more effective and dynamic pedagogical strategies.

Keywords: Agile methodologies. Scrum. Kanban. Engineering Education. Literature Review.

1 Introduction

The demands of the modern world drive a continuous flow of innovation in society. In the academic context, universities have intensified their efforts to get closer to the business sector. The growing market demand has stimulated the transformation of classrooms, to ensure that students develop not only solid theoretical knowledge in their areas of study but also essential transversal skills fundamental for a complete professional performance aligned with contemporary demands (Castaño Urueña et al., 2024; Ogunrinde, 2022).

The literature shows some problems related to the traditional teaching model, where students are not able to solve problems, work in teams, and communicate. Assessment in the traditional teaching model consists of a process carried out at the end of the course, where the competence achieved is the ability to pass the final exam (Hansen & Luxhøj, 1995; Souza et al., 2019).

The agile approach, which originated in the context of Information Technology (IT), is now prominent in the educational context, where institutions teach agile methodologies and real-world scenarios to prepare and develop future professionals (Souza et al., 2022). Process agility and continuous learning have become important requirements for employees and organizations. Professionals have developed agile methodologies as an alternative to traditional models, based on the premise that every project, regardless of its size, has inherent complexity and is influenced by multiple variables and factors that may affect its development. These

methodologies also provide an alternative approach to conventional teaching methods (Castaño Urueña et al., 2024; López-Alcarria et al., 2019; Sharp & Lang, 2018).

Although the importance of agile methodologies in the professional context is well established, there are still knowledge gaps regarding their application in the academic environment. Given this scenario, this study seeks to answer the following research question: What are the most widely used agile methodologies in educational contexts? The study aims to analyze the applicability of agile methodologies in the traditional context.

Therefore, the study identified and analyzed the main agile methodologies applied in the professional contexts of engineering, management, business, and IT, and evaluated their adaptation to the academic environment. This study used a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) method, which maximizes the potential of a search by finding the highest possible number of results in a more organized way (Alfonso et al. 2021; Moher et al. 2009).

2 Reference Theoretical

2.1 Agile Methodologies

Agile methodologies originated from the Agile Manifesto, created by information technology (IT) professionals in 2001. Although initially focused on software development, they were soon applied to other fields, such as product development and project management (Cooper & Sommer, 2016; Könnölä et al., 2016; López-Alcarria et al., 2019; Mota et al., 2022; Xu & Koivumäki, 2019).

Several methods based on agile principles have since emerged, including Scrum, Kanban, eXtreme Programming (XP), Crystal, Dynamic Systems Development Method (DSDM), and Feature Driven Development (FDD). Among these, Scrum and Kanban are the most widely used. Their adoption allows organizations to respond quickly to changes, reduce development time and costs, increase team motivation, and promote collaboration and knowledge sharing (Cooper & Sommer, 2016; Könnölä et al., 2016; López-Alcarria et al., 2019; Mota et al., 2022; Xu & Koivumäki, 2019).

Scrum is one of the most popular agile methodologies. It organizes projects into time-limited cycles called sprints, typically lasting two to four weeks, which are repeated until project completion. Scrum teams include: (i) developers, responsible for the tasks; (ii) a Product Owner, who defines project requirements and manages backlogs; and (iii) a Scrum Master, who facilitates the process and removes obstacles (Sutherland, 2001; Schwaber & Sutherland, 2017; López-Alcarria et al., 2019).

Kanban, meaning "visual card" in Japanese, is a flexible approach that uses visual boards divided into columns such as "To Do", "In Progress", and "Done". It allows teams to track progress and manage tasks with greater visibility. Unlike Scrum, Kanban does not use fixed work cycles but limits the number of simultaneous tasks, helping prevent overload and identify bottlenecks. Kanban boards can be physical or digital, and tools like Trello are commonly used for remote collaboration (López-Alcarria et al., 2019).

2.2 Agile Methodologies in the Educational Context

Education involves various types of projects that require effective management to meet objectives. Given the success of agile methodologies in the private and public sectors, their integration into education has been gaining traction, particularly when compared to traditional teaching methods (López-Alcarria et al., 2019; Nuottila et al., 2016).

Agile methods are commonly introduced in education through Project-Based Learning (PBL), which fosters a student-centered approach and promotes interdisciplinary skills like teamwork and planning, increasing student motivation and engagement (Zapater et al., 2013).

A study by Zapater et al. (2013) applied Scrum in conjunction with PBL in two engineering courses, challenging students to develop a complex team project in which they applied the methodology to solve real-world problems. The research revealed that students who participated in this approach showed greater motivation, satisfaction, and engagement than students in courses using traditional methods. This dynamic learning model encourages cooperation and self-management, bringing students closer to practical situations similar to those experienced in the job market.

The study by Valentin et al. (2015) corroborates Zapater et al. (2013); they sought to develop several soft skills in an integrated manner, while minimizing disruption to students' academic routines. The team adopted the Scrum methodology and achieved significant results. The organization stood out among the main advances reported, as students realized that the precise definition of guidelines, roles, and structured events contributed to maintaining focus and motivation in research projects. In addition, communication also showed significant improvements, as the proposed structure facilitated interaction between students and researchers, making it more efficient and productive (López-Alcarria et al., 2019).

3 Methodology

This study employed a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) to achieve its research objectives. Data was collected from the Scopus and Web of Science databases, following a structured process:

- 1) Search for the terms (" agile methodologies *" OR " agile project management*" OR " agile frameworks*") in the databases.
- 2) Selection of articles published in journals.
- 3) Results were limited to fields of interest (Computer Science, Engineering and Business, Management and Accounting).
- 4) Results were limited to document types (Article and Review).
- 5) Results were limited to language (English).
- 6) Articles with the keyword agile methodologies in the abstract were selected.

The articles were analyzed according to the steps in Figure 1, presenting the Prisma Flowchart related to the database search. This flowchart follows the guidelines of the PRISMA model (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses), proposed by Moher et al. (2009), which guides the conduct and reporting of systematic reviews. It describes the study selection process, including the identification, screening, eligibility, and inclusion phases, and ensures greater transparency and reproducibility of the selected articles.

It is important to acknowledge a potential limitation regarding the choice of search terms. Although the expressions used ("agile methodologies*", "agile project management*", and "agile frameworks*") may not capture the full breadth of studies that intersect agile practices and educational contexts, they are believed to broadly encompass the most relevant contributions to the theme. This approach aimed to balance specificity and inclusivity, ensuring a representative sample of the literature available in the selected databases.

Figure 1. PRISMA method

4 Results and Discussion

The analysis of the twenty-seven (27) selected articles revealed that most applications of agile methodologies are concentrated in Information Technology (IT), representing 44% of the studies. This is followed by management and business contexts with 33% and engineering with only 11%.

The lower representation in areas such as education, management, and engineering suggests that these methodologies still face challenges adapting to contexts with more rigid structures, complex processes, or less dynamic organizational cultures. Therefore, it is necessary to analyze how IT learning can be transferred to other contexts, considering the specificities of each context (Bakar & Dorasamy, 2023; Soares et al., 2022; López-Alcarria et al., 2019).

4.1 Benefits and Challenges of Agile Methodologies in the Educational Context

López-Alcarria et al. (2019) highlighted that there is empirical evidence in the literature on the application of agile methodologies in education. This evidence shows how agile methodologies have become a topic of growing interest in several fields, including the educational context, with an exponential number of experiments and experiences reported in recent years.

The main benefits of adopting agile methodologies in education are the acquisition of skills such as critical thinking, uncertainty management, effective communication, respect for opinions, collaborative work, dialogue, responsibility, and systemic thinking. These skills are essential for the personal and professional development of students and prepare them to face the challenges of the job market (López-Alcarria et al., 2019).

In support of these findings, Elgueta (2016) conducted a study in higher education in software engineering using agile methodologies such as Scrum and Kanban in the context of service learning. The study aimed to

train students to develop software using agile methods. The results indicated that students developed relevant skills, such as the analytical ability to solve complex problems and to work effectively in teams.

These studies demonstrate that agile methodologies, particularly Scrum and Kanban, can be effectively applied in higher education. These practices foster technical skills and significantly enhance behavioral competencies, making them valuable tools for teaching and learning (Elgueta, 2016; López-Alcarria et al., 2019).

Due to several barriers, the implementation of agile methodologies in industries outside of the traditional information technology (IT) domain remains a significant challenge. One of the main barriers is related to investment in training, which is essential for teams to understand the theoretical foundations of agile methodologies and their practical application in different contexts. Many organizations are reluctant to allocate financial resources and time to train their teams, especially in sectors where the concept of agility is not yet widely recognized as a strategic differentiator.

Table 1 presents the benefits and challenges of applying these methodologies

Table 1. Benefits and Challenges of applying Agile Methodologies

Authors	Context	Methodologies Agile	Main Benefits	Main Challenges
Álvarez & Roibás-Millán, 2021 Soares et al., 2022 Soueid & Cora Martins, 2021	Engineering	SCRUM, FDD, ASD, XP, DSDM, CRISTAL	Reduction in development time Resource optimization.	Project complexity Resistance to change
Larson & Chang, 2016 Nerur et al., 2005 Özkan & Mishra, 2019 Riaz et al., 2018 Ríos & Pedreira-Souto, 2019	Information Technology (IT)	Extreme Programming (XP), SCRUM, KANBAN, Scrum for safety	Flexibility and Adaptability Collaboration and Communication Speed and Efficiency, Product Quality	Complexity of tools Team competence Resistance to change
Castaño Urueña et al., 2024 Lopez-Alcarria et al., 2019 Zapater et al., 2013	Education	SCRUM, KANBAN	Greater student engagement Continuous feedback Improved collaboration Adaptability, creativity	Planning overload Resistance to change Time Management
Abukhamis & Abdelhadi, 2022 Ahsan & Ho, 2024 Aránega et al., 2023 Bakar & Dorasamy, 2023 Lishner & Shtub, 2023 Mota et al., 2022 Nyman & Öörni, 2023 Stormi et al., 2019 Suarez-Gomez & Hoyos - Vallejo, 2023	Management and Business	SCRUM, LEAN, BUSINESS MODEL CANVAS, DESIGN THINKING, LEAN KANBAN	Acceleration in Development Improved resource utilization Increase in productivity	Adapting the tools Team Engagement, Risk Management

According to Table 1, in education, approaches such as Kanban and Scrum combined with Project-Based Learning (PBL) have demonstrated the potential to transform pedagogical processes, promoting greater student engagement, improved collaboration, and continuous feedback. However, implementing these methodologies faces difficulties related to planning, which is often overloaded, and time management, especially for educators unfamiliar with agile practices (López-Alcarria et al., 2019; Zapater et al., 2013).

A study by Barbosa et al. (2019) corroborates these findings. The study involved a project to introduce Scrum in the context of PBL with university students. Feedback from the students revealed the benefits of the application, including improved understanding of task division, organization, and teamwork.

Adapting agile methodologies in the educational environment can bring several benefits, such as greater flexibility in learning, improved collaboration between students and teachers, and more dynamic teaching that

adapts to individual needs. These methodologies, widely used in the business sector to optimize processes and increase efficiency, can promote more interactive teaching, stimulate student autonomy, and facilitate curricular adaptation according to the challenges and changes of the modern world (López-Alcarria et al., 2019; Zapater et al., 2013).

Table 2 presents the adaptations of agile methodologies for application in educational contexts.

Table 2. Adaptation of agile methodologies to the educational context

Authors	Methodology Agile	Main Focus	Application General	Adaptation for Education
López-Alcarria et al., 2019 Schwaber & Sutherland, 2017 Sutherland, 2001	Scrum	Organization and collaboration	Iterative project management with sprints	Time management and academic tasks
Lopez-Alcarria et al., 2019	Kanban	Flow transparency continuum	Visual workflow management	Using Kanban boards for learning
Baltador et al., 2024 Mayer & Schwemmler, 2024	Design Thinking	Creativity	Problem-solving with a user-centered approach	Creating solutions for teaching

Table 2 shows that while each methodology has a specific focus, all can be adapted to make education more efficient. Scrum facilitates the organization of academic tasks by structuring activities into well-defined phases, providing greater predictability and control over student progress. Kanban improves visual management by allowing both students and teachers to monitor the progress of activities in real time, facilitating the identification of difficulties and agile decision-making to adjust the process. Design thinking promotes creativity in the search for innovative solutions and encourages critical thinking and experimentation, essential elements for more active and engaging teaching (Baltador et al., 2024; López-Alcarria et al., 2019).

Thus, the selection and combination of these methodologies can improve the educational experience and autonomy of students. Integrating these approaches enables a more flexible, collaborative, and efficient learning environment in which students assimilate content and develop fundamental skills in problem-solving, work organization, and adaptation to different educational contexts. Thus, the implementation of these methodologies in the educational environment can lead to a result in more dynamic, motivating teaching aligned with learning needs (Baltador et al., 2024; López-Alcarria et al., 2019; Zapater et al., 2013).

5 Conclusion

This study presented agile methodologies in different application contexts, identifying Scrum and Kanban as the primary methodologies used in academic settings. The applicability of these approaches in educational environments demonstrates benefits such as increased student engagement, the development of behavioral skills, and flexible adaptation to students' needs.

However, the implementation of these methodologies still faces relevant challenges, such as the need for teacher training, resistance to change, and the need for adjustments to traditional pedagogical models. To overcome these barriers, it is essential for educational institutions to invest in continuous training programs, promote collaborative environments for methodological experimentation, and encourage the gradual adoption of these practices through pilot projects supported by systematic evaluations.

Furthermore, a gap in the literature can be observed regarding the direct comparison between agile and traditional teaching methods, as well as the assessment of their impacts across different educational levels and

areas of knowledge. There is also limited discussion about their practical application in institutions with rigid structures or low technological maturity. Future studies could explore these gaps by investigating, for example, the effectiveness of using Scrum and Kanban in primary or technical education, or in humanities courses, and by evaluating the long-term effects on learning and skill development.

Additionally, as a future perspective, it is important to compare the use of agile methodologies in education with their application in organizational environments. This comparison may reveal more realistic adaptation opportunities, considering that educational settings have structural and cultural particularities, such as individualized evaluation systems and institutional resistance to curricular changes. Studies combining active methodologies with traditional approaches may also contribute to the development of more effective hybrid models.

It is therefore concluded that adapting agile methodologies to the educational reality is not only feasible but necessary to promote training that is more aligned with contemporary demands. The integration of these practices can make education more dynamic, interactive, and student-centered, contributing to the creation of more effective and engaging learning environments.

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